

**SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE ROLE OF AZAD
SHARAFIDDINOV'S RESEARCH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF OUR
LITERARY STUDIES**

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Azad Sharafiddinov is one of the skilled exponents of the Uzbek intelligentsia, an outstanding scientist, publicist, translator. Azad Sharafiddinov entered literature in the 60s of the last century with a unique appearance. His topical articles on the problems of fiction, especially the book “Time, spirit, poetry”, brought a new breath to Uzbek literature. The scientist's artistic and critical works, written with a fiery heart, exactingness, in-depth scientific research about the outstanding Uzbek writer and poets, made a huge contribution to the development of our literature.

Azad Sharafiddinov is a professor who, in addition to his main scientific and pedagogical activities, has been active in the spiritual and social spheres. Thus, he effectively worked on the education and formation of young talents. The scientist worked tirelessly at the National University of Uzbekistan for forty years, was a caring and attentive teacher.

Azad Sharafiddinov served as deputy editor-in-chief of the magazine “Tafakkur” from 1996 to 1997, and as editor-in-chief of the magazine “World literature” from 1997 to the end of his life. During this period, he proved to be a wise leader and a talented translator, in his translation rare works of world literature were published on the pages of magazines.

Azad Sharafiddinov engaged in active, selfless creativity, especially during the years of independence. Despite suffering from a serious illness, as a literary critic and publicist, he created such wonderful works as “independence fighters”, “Chulpon's awareness”, “thoughts on the river”, “President”, “happiness of creative knowledge”.

The services of Azad Sharafiddinov to the people and the country were duly noted. He was awarded the titles "hero of Uzbekistan", "honored scientist of Uzbekistan", "labor fame", "for great services", laureate of the State prize named after Beruniy.

Azad Sharafiddinov dealt with the problems of poetry for Uzbek literature, wrote literary-critical articles about Uzbek poetry and its state, and these articles provide a great opportunity for Uzbek literature. His scientific-creative, literary-critical research at the time was "contemporary. Heart. Poetry" (1962). In the 60s and 80s of the 20th century, he sought to promote the life and work of the Steppe man. Azad Sharafiddinov created literary portraits of Uzbek literary figures such as Oybek, Ghafur Ghulam, Abdullah Qahhor, Shaykhzoda, Mirtemir, Zulfiya: "the jilar of talent" (1976), "literary etyuds" (1968), "Abdullah Qahhor" (1988), "the first miracle" (1979). An important place in the work of Azad Sharafiddinov is occupied by the literary-critical book of ocherks "Yalovbardors" (1974), which was created about the work of other literary figures.

Azad Sharafiddinov reflected cases in the Uzbek literary process from the 60s to the 19th centuries in his works "talent - folk property" (1979), "literature – a textbook of life" (1981), "in search of beauty" (1985), "loyalty to truth" (1988), "Sardaftar pages" (1999), "President" (2003).

Azad Sharafiddinov can be said to be a person who has endowed life with science and literature. During the years of independence, Azad Sharafiddinov carried out tremendous work both as a literary critic, translator and public figure. "Chulpan" (1991), "understanding Chulpan" (1994), and "why I changed my faith" (1997) reflect munaqqid's aesthetic principles. In the following years, Azad Sharafiddinov wrote dozens of articles about Uzbek writer, cultural-art figures, scientists. He translated the works of many figures of world literature into Uzbek. "A piece of sun in puddle water" (Françoise Sagan), "examples of ancient Chinese prose", "Monumental Propaganda" (Vl. Boynovich), "Al-Khimik" (Paulo Koel'o) Singari.

The culmination of Azad Sharafiddinov's work is the book "happiness of understanding creativity" (2004). In it, the role of Uzbek literature in the world literary process and scientific and spiritual subjects were studied. Prominent literary critic, professor Azad Sharafiddinov is an irreplaceable person who has his own opinion, his own interpretation and critical views in literary debates and discussions. We must learn from them loyalty to the motherland, unlimited love for Literature, dedication to the profession. For the rest of his life, the teacher emphasized that love for the Motherland should be pure, noble, invulnerable, free from any bragging, artificiality. Azad Sharafiddinov said: "Let not a single soul, who has not heard the dovrug of Uzbekistan, has not heard of the definition of a paradise land called Uzbekistan. Only when we say that we are Uzbeks, let us keep our Destiny upright for our contribution to the prosperity of this beautiful land. We must follow the above verses. In the nature of Azad Sharafiddinov there is tolerance and courage inherent in great scientists. Being able to revise itself, even if there is a shortage of seeds, not everyone can raise it to the status of open recognition. In particular, to question himself, "Why did I change my faith", in a ring with a flame, in which worldviews face evrishment, a person must first of all be valiant. The recognition of the truth of thoughts, written down in his scientific articles or books, which seemed correct in time, changed over time, is also a quality inherent in a truly joemard scientist. Looking at the work of Azad Sharafiddinov, the places worthy of such a sign are clearly visible. In particular, in the article "literature lives — nation lives", Chulpan openly writes that his article "The Government of the desert and sanoe nafisa "as evidence of the poet's" positive welcome to the revolution", put forward the assumption that "genius "is a work" influenced by certain works", and his opinion changed after acquaintance with new sources.

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